

BIOINDICATORS: A KEY APPROACH TO ENVIRONMENTAL POLLUTION DETECTION

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ABSTRACT

The environment quality of water, soil and air is degraded increasingly. Therefore, it is essential to strengthen the prevention of pollution efforts by continuous monitoring of environmental quality. Biological methods evaluate environmental quality by examining the presence and diversity of various organisms, including plants, insects, fish, bacteria and viruses which serve as bioindicators. Specific bacterial species have been served as biological indicators for monitoring environmental health. The bacteria act as an indicator of household waste (human and animal faeces, household waste). Bioindicators refer to living organisms like planktons, plants, animals, and microorganisms, which are employed to determine the ecological status of the environment. They are utilized for evaluating environmental health and tracking biogeographical changes occurring in the ecosystems. All living entities within a biological system provide an insight into the quality of environment around them. In this review we have tried to explain the concept behind Bioindicators and plankton, with particular emphasis on their potential to be used as Bioindicators for water quality assessment and outcomes relating to this.

Keywords: Ecosystems, Bioindicators, Pollution, Monitoring

INTRODUCTION

Bioindicators are the organisms such as plants, lichens, planktons, birds, animals, bacteria and microbes etc. which have the ability to assess the condition of the environment. When the birds stop chirping and go hiding, you can expect a storm. When the ants begin to march, you know rain is on its way. Similarly, certain plant and animal species show responses that signal possible environmental degradation, act as early warning systems or bio-indicators of pollution. Naturally occurring Bioindicators are used to detect the changes in the environment, analyse the environmental pollution and their consequent effects on human society. The use of these biological indicators is an emerging approach that scientists are increasingly employing to gauge the level of environmental pollution.

With the help of Bioindicators, the degree of contamination can be monitored in a particular substance (Khatri & Tyagi 2015). Bioindicators help us to know the cumulative effects of various pollutants in the environment and also about the longevity of the problem. Bioindicators act as a significant biomarker for monitoring the quality of water as well as detector of water pollution. Planktons are powerful bioindicator as they reflect the health of aquatic vegetation and thus act as an early warning signal. Some specific physiological and

behavioral changes occur in the bioindicators which are used to monitor the changes in environmental health and these particular changes differ from one organism to another organism. Bioindicators are economically viable substitute in comparison to the other specialized measuring systems.

TYPES OF BIOINDICATORS

Bioindicators are used to handle biomonitoring and assess human effect on the environment. Bioindicators are sub-divided mainly into Plant indicators, Animal indicators and Microbial indicators.

PLANT INDICATORS

Plants are very sensitive indicators which are used for prediction and detection of environmental stresses and provide significant clues about the health of the environment. Lichens, Mosses, tree rings, tree bark and leaves are some of the important bioindicators. The environmental health can be easily determined by the presence or absence of some particular plants. Both lichens and bryophytes are reliable indicators of air pollution at the terrestrial level as they quantitatively assess the accumulation of heavy metals in the atmosphere. (Holt & Miller 2010; Thakur et al. 2013). They respond to ecological changes occurring in the forests such as changes in the structure of the forest and various other climatic changes. The increase in the concentration of pollutants of nitrogen (N₂) and sulfur dioxide (SO₂) leads to the disappearance of lichens in the forests which indicates about the environmental stresses (Peterson 1986; Gerhardt 2002; Khatri & Tyagi 2015). *Wolffia globosa* is a powerful bioindicator which is used for detecting cadmium contamination. Cynophyta, commonly known as blue-green algae is a kind of phytoplankton, is one of the powerful bioindicator which indicates eutrophication of water bodies such as ponds, lakes, reservoirs, etc. by the formation of algal blooms (Walsh 1978; Thakur et al. 2013). Marine plants such as sea grasses, coral reefs, seaweed, marsh grasses etc. indicate the condition of oceanic environment, by obtaining equilibrium with their natural environment (Phillips & Rainbow 1993; De Lange 1994; Jain et al. 2010).

ANIMAL INDICATORS

Fluctuations in animal populations may indicate detrimental environmental changes resulting from pollution within the ecosystem. Changes in the population density may indicate negative impacts to the ecosystem (Plafkin et al. 1989; Phillips & Rainbow 1993; Jain et al. 2010). Animal indicators also utilized for determining the quantities of toxins accumulated in animal tissues (Joanna 2006; Khatri & Tyagi 2015). Frogs also serve as bioindicators of environmental quality and ecological changes. Frogs are basically influenced by changes that take place in their freshwater and terrestrial habitats. Zooplanktons like *Alona guttata*, *Mesocyclops edax*, *Cyclops*, *Aheyella* are zone-based indicators of pollution (Underwood & Shapiro 1999; Hans et al. 2003; Pradhan et al. 2008; Zannatul & Muktedir 2009; Jain et al. 2010; Nkwoji et al. 2010; Hosmani 2014).

Invertebrates can likewise serve as Bioindicators. Many aquatic invertebrates tend to be bottom feeders (also referred to as Benthos) that inhabit at the base of water bodies can be especially effective in assessing watershed health and reflect the cumulative effects of ecological conditions (Plafkin et al. 1989; Khatri & Tyagi 2015).

MICROBIAL INDICATORS

Microorganisms act as Bioindicators to detect the health of terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems. Microorganisms are easily available as they are found in large amount. The stress proteins produced by some microorganisms on exposure to benzene and cadmium contaminants are used as early warning signals (Khatri & Tyagi 2015). Microorganisms have a fast growth rate, and they respond to even low quantity of contaminants and various other biological and physicochemical and changes (Jha & Barat 2003; Markert et al. 2003; Ramchandra et al. 2006; Pradhan et al. 2008; Zannatul & Muktedir 2009; Hosmani 2014). Microbial indicators are used in various ways to detect water pollutants including bioluminescent bacteria. The water contaminants can be simply monitored by the disruption in the digestive system of microbes which is inhibited by the toxins present in water and this may result in quantitative change in the emission of light by the bacteria (Arora 1966; Butterworth et al. 2001; Uttah et al. 2008). This method of water testing is very fast and easy as compared to various other traditional testing methods. But this method has one limitation also as it only signify the changes in organisms which occur due to the presence of toxins (Malik & Bharti 2012; Khatri & Tyagi 2015).

For example, the bacterium *Vogesella Indigofera* responds to heavy metals rapidly. In the presence of hexavalent chromium, the pigment production is blocked in the bacteria which would otherwise produce blue pigmentation in case of no metal pollution. This is a significant indication of morphological change that can be easily observed visually. Thus this bacteria act as powerful bioindicator in case of metal pollutants by changes in the pigment production. (Grizzle 1984; Jain et al. 2010; Aslam et al. 2012; Malik & Bharti 2012).

BIOMONITORING

Biomonitoring or Bioindicators are basically used to describe the characteristics of an environment. Commonly, the terms "biomonitoring" and "bioindication" are almost similar, but scientifically both these terms have different meanings (Mohapatra & Mohanty 1992; Gaston 2000; Lilian 2009; Offem et al. 2011). Bioindicators determine the changes taking place in the quality of the environment while biomonitors are used to detect quantitative information of the changes taking place in the environment (Noss 1990; Gaston 2000; Chakraborty & Paratkar 2006).

In biological monitoring, the species diversity is considered as an important factor in determining the condition of the environment (Marques 2001; Joanna 2006). Biomonitoring is one of the important mechanism for detecting the quality of water and help in the study related to water pollution (Vitousek et al. 1997; Butterworth et al. 2001). Biomonitors are found in abundance and are easily obtainable around the world. They be easily with least amount of preparation and training (Burger 1993; Green 1993; Siddiqui & Chandrasekhar 1996; Carignan & Villard 2001; Kumari et al. 2007; Fadila et al. 2009). For example, lichens are used as biomonitors which give the quantitative information of metal concentrations within the individual lichens.

WHAT MAKES A GOOD BIOINDICATOR?

There are approximately 1.7 million species currently present on the Earth. All the species cannot be used as a bioindicator and also no single species can indicate each kind of change or stress taking place in all environments. The suitable bioindicator species or group of species should be selected for monitoring the environmental changes depending upon the particular environment.

To be considered as a good bioindicator, species must have some specific characteristics. The bioindicator species should be present in abundance and are easily available. The species should be relatively stable in reasonable climatic and environmental changes. The species should have good indicator ability. They must provide quantifiable response and should be sensitive to any stress or disturbance but does not acquire mortality or accumulate any kind of pollutants from their environment directly. The bioindicators must react in proportion to the level of contamination or disturbance. The species should be stable, taxonomically well documented and their life history and ecology should be well understood. The bioindicators should be inexpensive and to survey.

BENEFITS AND DISADVANTAGES OF BIOINDICATORS

Bioindicators can be used for variety of biological systems to assess the health of an ecosystem. They give information about the various biological, physical, and chemical components of the world and detect the changes in health, density and composition from species level to the ecosystem level. Bioindicators have the capability to detect indirect biotic effects of various pollutants while many of the physical and chemical methods cannot. They are low-priced and economical as compared to various other chemical methods.

In spite of too many benefits, Bioindicators has some disadvantages also. In some conditions, it is difficult to distinguish natural variability from the changes that take place due to human impacts. Thus the application of bioindicators is limited to the heterogeneous environments. The population of a bioindicator species may be affected by the various factors such as competition, disease, predation, parasitism etc. rather than any stress or disturbance. This complicates the picture regarding the proper mechanisms of change. Also, the indicator ability of bioindicators is scale-dependent. For example, a large bioindicator (e.g., fish) cannot detect the biodiversity of the local community of insects. The bioindicator species have different requirements for habitat than the other species in the ecosystem. So, if we manage an ecosystem according to the particular habitat requirements of a bioindicator then one may fail to conserve rare species which have different requirements.

However, the overall purpose of bioindicators is to use a species either singly or in group, to evaluate the quality of an environment and to detect the changes that occur over time in an environment. The disadvantages of the bioindicators are completely overshadowed by their benefits.

WHY ARE BIOINDICATORS BETTER THAN TRADITIONAL METHODS?

There are various types of traditional chemical assays which directly measure various physical parameters of the environment such as temperature, light, salinity, pollutants, nutrients etc. whereas in case of bioindicators, the living organisms are used to evaluate the effects of both pollutants and habitat changes over time. The utilization of bioindicators is better than various other traditional methods. The bioindicators can analyse the residence time or life span of an organism in a specific ecosystem, which helps in knowing present, past, or future environmental conditions. However, many physical and chemical methods only describe conditions at the time of sampling. Sometimes, the contaminants may occur in very small amount. So, very sensitive technologies are required to assess such low concentrations which are highly expensive. However, the bioindicators can easily detect such small amount of contaminants.

Bioindicators have capability to detect indirect biotic impacts of pollutants whereas many chemical or physical methods cannot. After monitoring thousands of factors, scientists now

understand that the living organisms are itself the best predictor of the ecosystem changes to stress or disturbance. Moreover, the physical and chemical measurements simplify a complex response inherent in the species-rich habitats. Bioindicators depend on the complicated details of the ecosystems and use an aggregated response to express a dynamic representation of the environmental condition. Mostly the bioindicators are inexpensive as compared to various traditional methods.

CONCLUSION

Bioindicators can be used at different levels, from the cellular level to the ecosystem level, for detecting the changes that take place in a particular biological environment. Planktons are used as a significant part for monitoring health condition of water bodies. From this review, we conclude that bioindicators and biomonitors are the powerful tools for studying the effects of various external factors on an environment and to differentiate between the contaminated and uncontaminated areas. This information helps us to build up various strategies that can reduce such effects and protect the environment from degradation.

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